

A Non-Linear Phase-Only Algorithm for Active Sonar Signal Processing

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Abstract — In highly reverberant environments the standard signal processing chain for wideband active sonar may be improved by using a phase-only filter to perform replica correlation. Because of the significant distortion of the signal magnitude spectrum, the phase-only filter performs better in such adverse conditions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pulse compression of frequency or phase modulated active transmissions are typically used to achieve accurate localization in range. Ideally, matched filtering of such wide bandwidth signal produces a high processing gain that is proportional to the time-bandwidth product and a sharp output peak proportional to the reciprocal of the signal bandwidth against an additive Gaussian stationary background.

In practice, the main interference against successful active sonar target detection is the reverberation from the medium. Reverberation is due to random scattering of the transmitted signal from the medium's boundaries (surface and bottom of the ocean) and volumetric inhomogeneities [1]. To further complicate extracting the target echo from the reverberation, the spectrum of the desired echo return is very similar to the spectrum of the reverberation — the former tends to be a specular return that preserves the phase coherence while the latter tends to be random phase over the sonar pulse length.

A typical active sonar echo return exhibits a wide dynamic range, typically over 60 dB, between the beginning and the end of the receive gate. Some post detection data normalization is usually required to produce a uniform background for detection using a fixed threshold. For a multiple beam system that spans the azimuth space, a two-dimensional normalizer is usually used to produce a uniform background in the range-azimuth space to maintain a constant false alarm rate. These normalizer algorithms are usually computationally intensive and many have undesired side effects that may adversely affect the performance of

localization and classification algorithms down stream in the processing chain.

The algorithm proposed here eliminates the need for range and azimuthal data normalization after the matched filter by scaling the input signal prior to matched filtering (similar to an automatic gain control but operating as a function of the correlator FFT block size). This algorithm scales the input signal with the estimated energy level in each data block and applies a phase-only filter to perform replica correlation [2] with the input signal in the Fourier domain. Since the magnitude spectrum of the received echo is typically distorted, use of a phase-only filter does not sacrifice as much information as one would expect. In summary, this new processing algorithm has the advantages of reduction of processing time for computer implementation, preservation of the target highlight structure, sharp correlation peaks, and suppression of large area reverberation returns (sea mounts and/or sea surface and sea bottom).

A. Background

A typical active sonar system is capable of transmitting and processing wideband waveforms that may be useful to detect targets in reverberation limited shallow water environments. The standard signal processing does not take into account the filtering effects of the propagating environment. A modified replica correlation algorithm is proposed to enhance the detection performance of wideband active sonar in shallow water environments. To validate the performance of this algorithm, received echoes from a medium frequency (3000 Hz) active sonar operating in a shallow water area (50 fathoms) were processed using the standard and proposed algorithm to compare their performances using metrics that relate directly to the detection of underwater targets.

II. ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

A. Characteristics of the Transmitted Signal

The passband characteristics of the transmitted signal $s(t)$ is given by [3]

$$s(t) = A(t) \cos \left[\frac{2\pi f_0^2 T}{B} \ln \left(1 - \frac{Bt}{f_0 T} \right) \right]. \quad (1)$$

Expanding $\ln \left(1 - \frac{Bt}{f_0 T} \right)$ yields

$$s(t) = A(t) \cos \left[2\pi f_0 t + \frac{\pi B t^2}{T} + \frac{2\pi B^2 t^3}{3f_0 T^2} + \dots \right]. \quad (2)$$

The argument of Equation (2) is denoted as

$$\Phi(t) = \frac{2\pi f_0^2 T}{B} \ln\left(1 - \frac{Bt}{f_0 T}\right). \quad (3)$$

The instantaneous frequency is

$$\frac{d\Phi}{dt} = \frac{2\pi f_0^2 T}{f_0 T - Bt} = \frac{1}{\text{Period}}. \quad (4)$$

The reciprocal of $\frac{d\Phi}{dt}$ is the period

$$T_0 = \text{Period} = \frac{f_0 T - Bt}{2\pi f_0^2 T}, \quad (5)$$

where

B is the sweep bandwidth,
T is the pulse duration, and
 f_0 is the carrier frequency.

The spectrum of $s(t)$ in equation 2 is relatively flat over the bandwidth of the pulse. The linear period modulated (LPM) signal has slightly more energy in the beginning of the pulse (or the start frequency) since the sweep is hyperbolic instead of linear, as in the linear frequency modulated (LFM) pulse. The LPM affords a higher Doppler tolerance than the LFM, a property considered to be essential in open ocean operations. For shallow water operations, the LFM may be used without significant loss in Doppler tolerance; the intended targets are likely to be slow or stationary. Figure 1 shows the spectra of LPM and LFM pulses; both have pulse length of one second and sweep bandwidth of 400Hz.

Figure 1: Spectra of wideband angle modulated waveforms

B. Signal and Interference Models

Figure 2 shows the magnitude of a time series of a received phase modulated signal from the sonar's beamformer. The optimum filter to yield maximum peak signal-to-noise ratio for

$x(t)$ is the matched filter but this is true only if $x(t)$ is stationary and the interfering noise is white. For the active sonar case, these two assumptions are not satisfied and the replica correlator does not give the expected performance.

Figure 2: Envelope detected signal as seen at the beamformer of a typical active sonar. Note the wide dynamic range

If an echo return is contained in time interval $(t_1, t_1 + T)$, it can be modeled as the convolution between the transmit signal, $s(t)$, and $h_o(t)$. The function $h_o(t)$ is the convolution of the following impulse responses: the outbound environmental, the target, and the return trip environmental impulse response.

$$x(t) = s(t) * h_o(t) + \sum_{m=1}^M s(t) * h_m(t) + w(t), \quad t_1 < t < t_1 + T \quad (6)$$

The summation of terms represents the numerous reflections due to the volume, surface and bottom scatterers observed by the receiver during the same time interval T. The statistical characteristics of this sum of reverberation from the scatterers is random. Its magnitude may be assumed to have a Rayleigh distribution and its phase angle and time of arrival may be assumed to have uniform distributions. These assumptions are usually true if no dominant reverberation (e.g., reflection from sea mount close to the sonar) is present.

If the received signal $\{s(t) * h_o(t)\}$ is due to specular reflection from a submarine (cylindrical shape, with air backing), the phase of the signal should be relatively well preserved as compared to the summation with $h_m(t)$, the sum of many random variables. The ambient noise, $w(t)$, has a spectral density of N_0 and is normally below the reverberation level.

In the frequency domain, equation (6) may be written as:

$$X(\omega) = H_o(\omega)S(\omega) + \sum_{m=1}^M H_m(\omega)S(\omega) + W(\omega) \quad (7)$$

Consider a window of data length T in time containing the target; the filtering operation is equivalent to a frequency domain multiplication of $S(\omega)$ and $H_o(\omega)$. With no target

present, the received signal is a sum of the reverberation spectra from the scatterers and the ambient noise spectrum.

Replica correlation is the standard 'optimal' processing to detect the presence of known signal type from background interference. It is well known in matched filtering theory that if $s(t)$ is the transmitted signal, then the replica is $Ks^*(-t)$. The received signal is usually processed using an overlap-add or overlap-save FFT convolution algorithm.

The system model of a sonar system is shown below. The echo return consists of a target return plus the contribution from scatterers admitted into the beam pattern of the transducer. In a shallow water environment, numerous boundary interactions give rise to reverberation with a statistically well-behaved distribution, by way of the Central Limit Theorem.

Figure 3: Model of an active sonar system operating in reverberation-limited environment

The echo returns (reverberation or interference) from the scatterers is represented by

$$p(t) = \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m(t) s(t - \tau_m) e^{j\theta_m} \quad (8)$$

Phase: $\{\theta_m\} \sim$ uniformly distributed $[-\pi, \pi]$.

Magnitude: $\{\alpha_m\} \sim$ Rayleigh distributed.

Time Delay: $\{\tau_m\} \sim$ uniformly distributed in $\Delta T = \frac{\Delta R}{C}$.

The reverberation return is the summation of the echo return from these scatterers (equation 8). The received signal in a beamformed system is the summation of these time delayed, phase modified, amplitude modulated received signals.

Equation (8) may be rewritten compactly as

$$p(t) = \sum_{m=1}^M h_m(t) * s(t) \quad (9)$$

The channel impulse response, $h_m(t)$, describes the filtering effects on the reverberation returns by the wave propagating environment.

As mentioned before, replica correlation is the optimal processing to detect a known waveform in white noise. In practice, the assumptions for optimality are always violated. The exact environmental transfer function is usually not known in sufficient details to remove the effects of the environmental distortions to allow replica correlation to maximize the signal-to-noise ratio. Recent research in matched field processing attempt to model the propagating medium for accurate range and depth determination. The success of such techniques requires detailed knowledge of the environment which may be difficult to acquire and process in real time tactical situations.

The reverberation, $p(t)$, has the same power spectrum as the signal, albeit with random phase, which makes it difficult to suppress using frequency-selective filtering.

The standard digital signal processing chain to perform replica correlation and data normalization is shown in the figure 4.

Figure 4: The standard replica correlation processing chain for a known active sonar signal

The progression of standard replica correlation processing is:

- Overlap-Save FFT convolution with the reference,
- Reference is the replica of the transmitted signal, and
- Temporal (and sometimes spatial) normalizer used to produce a uniform noise background (CFAR).

Data normalization uses the adjacent time samples to estimate the background for each time cell as a divisor for that time

cell. It is the most time consuming step in the processing chain but it is essential to maintain a near constant false alarm rate.

C. Description of the proposed algorithm

The proposed processing algorithm will be described in the following sections. The motivation and analysis of the phase-only filter and input data scaling will be presented.

1) The phase-only filter

A variation of the standard replica correlation processing is introduced to enhance the detection performance of active wideband frequency or phase-modulated waveforms. The proposed algorithm is motivated by work done in optical information processing. We propose to replace the Fourier transform of the replica with just its phase spectrum, making it a phase-only filter. In replica correlation, the filter used is $s^*(-t)$, its Fourier transform is $S^*(\omega)$ or $|S(\omega)|\exp[-j\Theta_s(\omega)]$. The phase only filter retains the term $\exp[-j\Theta_s(\omega)]$ only. We write the phase-only filter as:

$$H_{PO}(\omega) = \exp[-j\Theta_s(\omega)] \quad (10)$$

This filter (eqn. 10) will pass all frequency components in the received band with equal magnitude response of unity. The phase-only filter is a partial information filter and theoretically has lower performance than an optimally matched filter. This filter will produce a correlation peak similar to that of a standard replica correlator. Phase-only filters are used in optical information processing systems because of the light efficiency. To understand why this partial information filter can actually perform better than the standard replica correlator, we must consider the characteristics of the received signal. Figure 7 shows the spectrum of the replica in comparison with the spectrum of a data window containing a valid target.

Figure 7: Comparison of a typical received spectrum and an undistorted spectrum of the replica

It can be seen that the interaction of the signal with the target and the environment has modified the spectrum of the received signal to a vast degree. The phase-only processing will weight the individual frequency components based on its received magnitude, thus, frequencies that are least attenuated will have strongest contributions to the correlator output. This algorithm will improve the signal-to-noise ratio relative to the replica correlator that assumes that the received spectrum has the same magnitude response as the undistorted signal.

2) Input Scaling

The proposed algorithm borrows another idea from optical information processing to prepare the input data. Because of the limited dynamic range of optical devices (such as spatial light modulator, or SLM) used in such application as the input devices, the input signals must be scaled accordingly. A typical solution is to divide the data points within each data window by the signal energy of that window. That is, if $X_N(k)$ is the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of an N-point input time series, the scaled version is given by

$$X_d(k) = N X_n(k) / \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} |X_n(k)|^2 \quad (11)$$

The input scaling eliminates the need for the spatial and temporal normalizers in the processing chain and results in great savings in processing time. An improvement to this scaling scheme is to scale an area of M beams by N time samples, thus yielding a more accurate estimate of the local background.

One disadvantage of this input scaling method exists when the signal-to-noise ratio at the beamformer is very high, in such case the high signal energy will be used to scale itself and result in a globally lower signal-to-noise ratio. However, in low signal-to-noise situations, this input scaling scheme works well enough to justify the elimination of the spatial and temporal normalizers.

3) Analysis of the phase-only filter

Consider an input data window containing a target echo, the output of the phase-only filter is represented in the frequency domain as

$$Y(\omega) = H_{PO}(\omega)X(\omega) \quad (12)$$

where

$$X(\omega) = H_s(\omega)S(\omega) + \sum_{n=1}^N H_n(\omega)S(\omega) + W(\omega) \quad (13)$$

$$\text{and } H_{PO}(\omega) = \exp[-j\Theta_s(\omega)] \quad (14)$$

Denoting

$$P(\omega) = \sum_{m=1}^N H_m(\omega) S(\omega),$$

and combining equations 12, 13 and 14 yield

$$Y(\omega) = \exp[-j\Theta_s(\omega)] [S(\omega)H_o(\omega) + P(\omega)] \quad (15)$$

The ambient noise term, $W(\omega)$, has been dropped since $|W(\omega)| \ll |P(\omega)|$ for the reverberation limited environment. Expanding $R(\omega)$ and rearranging yield the following

$$Y(\omega) = \exp[-j\Theta_s(\omega)] \{ |S(\omega)| \exp[j\Theta_s(\omega)] H_o(\omega) + P(\omega) \} \quad (16)$$

The second term contains $P(\omega)$ which is the summation of numerous returns from random scatterers, and therefore it tends towards zero; the statistical expectation of equation (16) then reduces to

$$E[Y(\omega)] \approx |S(\omega)| H_o(\omega) \quad (17)$$

We further reduce equation (17) by noting that the magnitude spectrum of $S(\omega)$ is constant over the signal bandwidth (see figure 7), i.e., $|S(\omega)| H_o(\omega) = C H_o(\omega)$, where C is a constant; finally, rewriting equation (17) and setting $C = 1$, we get

$$E[Y(\omega)] \approx H_o(\omega) \quad (18)$$

Thus, the expected frequency spectrum of the phase-only filter output contains just the transfer function of the two-way propagating medium and the signal's interaction with the target.

D. Implementation of the proposed algorithm

Figure 8: Complex basebanding of an active sonar signal at the receiver

The basebanded sampled random process, $\{x(n)\}$ is generated from $x(t)$ by the demodulation and sampling processing shown in figure 8. The signal processing flowchart is shown in figure 9, the filtering operation is implemented using an overlap-add FFT algorithm. Each data window contains 2048 complex

samples (3.2 seconds in time). The phase only filter is 640 sample points in length (1.0 second in time).

Figure 9: Signal processing flowchart for the proposed algorithm

III. PROCESSING RESULTS

Forty-two (42) pings (target beam only) from a set of active sonar data collected in a shallow water environment were processed using first the standard processing of replica correlation and temporal normalizer, and second, the proposed processing, scaling by signal energy and filtering with Fourier phase only.

The peak deflection signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) were measured for each ping. The noise region used to estimate the background level was taken from a one-second time interval just prior to the echo return from the target. Table 1 summarizes the peak SNR results; the phase-only algorithm has the better results, its performance is better than the standard processing in 39 out of the 42 pings processed with an average improvement of 1.23 dB. The computer processing time required for the phase-only filter is less than 20% of that required by the standard processing. The saving in processing time will be more significant in a multi-beam sonar system where the standard spatial and temporal normalizers will be replaced by an area (M beam by L seconds) scaling scheme.

Table 1: Quarter Aspect Target, 10 kyds, 200-ft water depth, 42 pings, Area 'F'

(SNR in dB)	Standard	Phase Only
Mean SNR	18.78	20.01
Std Dev SNR	3.20	3.22
Min SNR	12.73	15.05
Max SNR	26.69	28.59
Median SNR	18.58	19.62
Execution speed ratio	1.00	0.18

The output time series from the two methods are presented in figure 11 and figure 12 (close-up). These two time series look similar, however, the phase-only algorithm produces a higher peak level than the standard processing. The relative strengths of the highlight structure is also preserved due to the response of the phase-only filter (see eqn. 18) and the elimination of the normalizer in the processing chain.

Figure 11: Output time series from the two processing methods (about 9 seconds shown, linear amplitude units)

Figure 12: Close-up of output time series from the two processing methods (2 seconds of data shown, linear amplitude units)

To supply the data points necessary to generate Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curves, single peak target echoes were injected into the 42 pings time series prior to replica correlation. The target echoes had a signal-to-noise ratio of -17 dB and were injected at 5 seconds and 7 seconds after the receive gate opens (there was reverberation only at these points). ROC curves generated using peak deflection SNRs and random noise samplings are presented in figures 13 and 14. In these figures with probability of false alarm as a function of threshold is represented by the leftmost curves and the probability of detection by the rightmost curves. It can be seen that the phase-only algorithm has higher probability of

detection for equal or lower probability of false alarm at those target ranges.

Figure 13: ROC curve for an injected target at t=5 seconds

Figure 14: ROC curve for an injected target at t=7 seconds

IV. CONCLUSION

An algorithm has been presented which demonstrates higher peak deflection signal-to-noise ratios with significant reduction in execution speed over standard replica correlation. The algorithm functions effectively in reverberation limited conditions.

REFERENCES

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